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тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

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Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918

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дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

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кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии,
неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2
Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
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Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентского государственного
стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры
онкологии Самаркандского государственного
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

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*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
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Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ibragimova Malika Xudayberganovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxamatkulovich

*DSc, Associate Professor of Oncology,
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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

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TURAEV Tolib Makhmudjonovich
basic doctoral student
KUCHIMOVA Charos Azamatovna
PhD
Samarkand State Medical University

CLINICAL SIGNIFICANS OF ANXIETY AND DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS IN PATIENTS WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME

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ABSTRACT

Currently, depression is increasingly considered as one of the triggers in the development of metabolic syndrome. This is due to the fact that affective disorders contribute to the formation of risk factors, which, according to the recommendations of the All-Russian Scientific Society of Cardiology for the diagnosis and treatment of metabolic syndrome, lead to the development of metabolic disorders. The main risk factors are: overeating, physical inactivity and hypertension.

And indeed, in a state of depression, the physical activity decreases, appetite increases, and hyperreactivity of the sympathetic nervous system (sympathicotonic syndrome) is a trigger factor for increased blood pressure. The fact that the association between depression and metabolic syndrome is a "two-way street" is confirmed by the results of a prospective cohort study of Whitehall II in 2009, which was performed by T.N. Akbaralya et al. Epidemiological studies are currently represented by data from samples of patients with metabolic syndrome quite large volumes. The most representative are the studies published in 2004 by L.S. Kinder et al. The authors of the work, which analyzed the material collected over 6 years, indicate that in a group of 3003 examined people aged 17 to 39 years, the proportion of people with metabolic syndrome is 2 times higher in cases where there is a history of an episode of depressive disorder. L. Witterberg et al. proposed the concept of "low melatonin syndrome" in patients with depressive disorders. According to this model, low melatonin levels may be the main reason for a decrease in the levels of norepinephrine and serotonin in the brain and indirectly affect the dysfunction of the hypothalamic-pituitary system, which in turn can be used as a marker of predisposition to the development of depressive disorders. At the same time, there are works discussing the role of melatonin in the development of dysmetabolism. In recent years, there has been an increase in patients with metabolic syndrome, which is a significant medical problem. The severity of clinical manifestations of metabolic syndrome affects the quality of life of patients, while physical and mental health indicators decrease. Obesity leads to anxiety disorders, neurosis-like conditions and depression, which contributes to the deterioration of the underlying disease. The available clinical and experimental data convincingly show the presence of multiple pathophysiological links that explain the high probability of the formation of metabolic syndrome in people with anxiety and depressive disorders.

ТУРАЕВ Толиб Махмуджонович
Базовой докторант
КУЧИМОВА Чарос Азаматовна
PhD

Самаркандский государственный медицинский университет

КЛИНИЧЕСКОЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ТРЕВОЖНЫХ И ДЕПРЕССИВНЫХ РАССТРОЙСТВ У ПАЦИЕНТОВ С МЕТАБОЛИЧЕСКИМ СИНДРОМОМ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В настоящее время депрессия все чаще рассматривается как один из триггеров развития метаболического синдрома. Это связано с тем, что аффективные расстройства способствуют формированию факторов риска, которые, согласно рекомендациям Всероссийского научного общества кардиологов по диагностике и лечению метаболического синдрома, приводят к развитию метаболических нарушений. Основными факторами риска являются: переизбыток, гиподинамия и гипертония. И действительно, в состоянии депрессии снижается физическая активность, повышается аппетит, а гиперреактивность симпатической нервной системы (симпатикотонический синдром) является пусковым фактором для повышения кровяного давления. Тот факт, что связь между депрессией и метаболическим синдромом является "улицей с двусторонним движением", подтверждается результатами проспективного когортного исследования Whitehall II в 2009 году, которое было проведено Т.Н. Akbaralya и соавт. Эпидемиологические исследования в настоящее время представлены данными выборки пациентов с метаболическим синдромом довольно больших объемов. Наиболее репрезентативными являются исследования, опубликованные в 2004 году L.S. Kinder и соавт. Авторы работы, проанализировавшие материал, собранный за 6 лет, указывают, что в группе из 3003 обследованных людей в возрасте от 17 до 39 лет доля людей с метаболическим синдромом в 2 раза выше в случаях, когда в анамнезе имеется эпизод депрессивного расстройства. Л. Виттерберг и др. предложено понятие "синдром низкого содержания мелатонина" у пациентов с депрессивными расстройствами. Согласно этой модели, низкий уровень мелатонина может быть основной причиной снижения уровней норадреналина и серотонина в головном мозге и косвенно влиять на дисфункцию гипоталамо-гипофизарной системы, что, в свою очередь, может быть использовано в качестве маркера предрасположенности к развитию депрессивных расстройств. В то же время существуют работы, в которых обсуждается роль мелатонина в развитии дисметаболизма. В последние годы наблюдается увеличение числа пациентов с метаболическим синдромом, который является серьезной медицинской проблемой. Тяжесть клинических проявлений метаболического синдрома влияет на качество жизни пациентов, при этом показатели физического и психического здоровья снижаются. Ожирение приводит к тревожным расстройствам, невротическим состояниям и депрессии, что способствует ухудшению течения основного заболевания. Имеющиеся клинические и экспериментальные данные убедительно свидетельствуют о наличии множественных патофизиологических связей, объясняющих высокую вероятность формирования метаболического синдрома у людей с тревожными и депрессивными расстройствами.

Ключевые слова: тревога, депрессия, метаболический синдром, ожирение, особенности лечения.

TURAEV Tolib Mahmudjonovich
Таянч докторант
KUCHIMOVA Charos Azamatovna
PhD
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti

METABOLIK SINDROMLI BEMORLARDA VAHIMALI VA DEPRESSIV BUZILISHLARNING KLINIK AHAMIYATI

ANNOTATSIYA

Hozirgi vaqtda depressiya metabolik sindrom rivojlanishining qo'zg'atuvchilaridan biri sifatida tobora ko'proq ko'rilmog'da. Buning sababi shundaki, affektiv buzilishlar Butunrossiya kardiologiya ilmiy jamiyatining metabolik sindromni tashxislash va davolash bo'yicha tavsiyalariga muvofiq metabolik kasalliklarning rivojlanishiga olib keladigan xavf omillarini shakllantirishga yordam beradi. Asosiy xavf omillari: ortiqcha ovqatlanish, jismoniy harakatsizlik va gipertoniya. Darhaqiqat, depressiya holatida jismoniy faollik pasayadi, ishtaha kuchayadi va simpatik asab tizimining giperreaktivligi (simpatikotonik sindrom) qon bosimini ko'tarish uchun qo'zg'atuvchi omil hisoblanadi. Depressiya va metabolik sindrom o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik "ikki tomonlama ko'cha" ekanligi 2009 yilda T. N. Akbaraliya va boshqalar tomonidan o'tkazilgan Whitehall II kohort tadqiqotining natijalari bilan tasdiqlangan. Epidemiologik tadqiqotlar hozirda juda katta hajmdagi metabolik sindromli bemorlarning namunalari ma'lumotlari bilan taqdim etilgan. Eng vakili 2004 yilda L. S. Kinder va boshqalar tomonidan nashr etilgan tadqiqotlardir. 6 yil davomida to'plangan materialni tahlil qilgan ish mualliflarining ta'kidlashicha, 17 yoshdan 39 yoshgacha bo'lgan 3003 nafar tekshirilgan odamlar guruhida metabolik sindromli odamlarning ulushi depressiv buzilish epizodi bo'lgan hollarda 2 baravar yuqori. L. Vitterberg va boshqalar. depressiv kasalliklarga chalingan bemorlarda "past melatonin sindromi" tushunchasi taklif qilingan. Ushbu modelga ko'ra, melatoninning past darajasi miyada norepinefrin va serotonin darajasining pasayishining asosiy sababi bo'lishi mumkin va bilvosita gipotalamus-gipofiz tizimining disfunktsiyasiga ta'sir qilishi mumkin, bu esa o'z navbatida depressiv kasalliklarning rivojlanishiga moyillik belgisi sifatida ishlatilishi mumkin. Shu bilan birga, melatoninning dismetabolizm rivojlanishidagi rolini muhokama qiladigan ishlar mavjud. So'nggi yillarda metabolik sindromli bemorlar sonining ko'payishi kuzatilmoqda, bu jiddiy tibbiy muammo. Metabolik sindromning klinik ko'rinishlarining og'irligi bemorlarning hayot sifatiga ta'sir qiladi, jismoniy va ruhiy salomatlik ko'rsatkichlari pasayadi. Semirib ketish Anksiyete kasalliklariga, nevrozga o'xshash holatlarga va depressiyaga olib keladi, bu esa asosiy kasallikning yomonlashishiga yordam beradi. Mavjud klinik va eksperimental dalillar tashvish va depressiv kasalliklarga chalingan odamlarda metabolik sindromning paydo bo'lish ehtimoli yuqori ekanligini tushuntiruvchi bir nechta patofiziologik bog'lanishlar mavjudligini aniq ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: vahima, depressiya, metabolik sindrom, semirish, davolash xususiyatlari.

Introduction: Metabolic syndrome is characterized by the presence of several significant risk factors for cardiovascular pathology, including central type obesity, hyperglycemia, dyslipidemia and arterial hypertension. All these risk factors are associated not only with cardiovascular diseases, but also with high morbidity and an unfavorable course of diabetes Type II The prevalence of MC is progressively increasing in both developed and in developing countries, creating increasing challenges to the health systems of many countries, including the Russian Federation. Currently, the prevalence of MS in adult populations is 25-30%. Identification and detailed study of possible modifiable risk factors It is the most important goal of modern clinical medicine.

Research methods: MS unites a group of diseases or pathological conditions manifested by certain metabolic, hormonal and clinical disorders, which is characterized by arterial hypertension, an increase in visceral fat mass, a decrease in the sensitivity of peripheral tissues to insulin (insulin resistance) and hyperinsulinemia, which cause disorders of carbohydrate, lipid and purine metabolism. It has been proven that the virsions of the metabolic changes are: arterial hypertension, insulin resistance with basal hyperrinsulinemia, dyslipidemia (an increase in triglycerides or a decrease in cholesterol, high-density lipoproteins, impaired glucose tolerance or diabetes mellitus type 2, abdominal obesity. In addition, women with metabolic syndrome need special attention from the sides of general practitioners in terms of the diagnosis of depressive disorders (DR), since in such patients depressive disorders are more common in comparison with patients without metabolic syndrome. Others aggravate the course of somatic disease, timely diagnosis and treatment of

depressive states will increase adherence to therapy with metabolic syndrome, thereby positively affecting the overall cardiovascular risk. Worldwide, at least 2.8 million people die each year as a result of being overweight or obese. It should be noted that overweight and obesity are the result of the formation of excessive body fat, which can be harmful to health. Mass ratio it is used to diagnose obesity and overweight in adults – body mass index (BMI). It is calculated as the ratio of body weight in kilograms to the square of height in meters (kg/m^2). According to WHO, the diagnosis of "overweight" or "obesity" in adults is determined by: overweight – BMI greater than or equal to 25; obesity – BMI greater than or equal to 30.

The results of the study: It is well known that the complex of pathophysiological processes that make up MS has a mutually influencing and multifactorial etiology, including many genetic, environmental and personal factors, including psychological personality traits. In recent years, it has been convincingly shown that psychological factors such as anxiety disorders and depression are significantly more common in MS than in the general population, even adjusted for traditional risk factors for these psychopathological conditions. It is known that anxiety disorders are the most common borderline psychiatric conditions in the population, whose the prevalence, calculated for 12 months of follow-up, is 9.3%, while when calculating the lifetime probability, the risk of developing an anxiety disorder will be 13.4%. The formed anxiety disorder plays an important role in limiting the physical activity of an individual and significantly reduces the quality of his life, leads to weight gain. It is often associated with overeating. Taken together, these factors inevitably lead to an increase in body weight, one of the most important components of MS, triggering a cascade of complementary metabolic processes. The specified relationship there is experimental confirmation. Such data were confirmed in a recent survey involving residents of 17 countries, which showed that anxiety disorders were associated with a very wide range of functional psychosomatic problems that limit physical activity. Based on the data obtained from the study of migrants of the extreme In the North with hypertension, a high incidence of anxiety-depressive symptoms has been established, the frequency and severity of which increases with age, hile women migrants of Extreme Northerners are prone to depression 1.9 times more often, anxiety 3.1 times more often than men. It was found that the frequency of occurrence of individual components of the metabolic syndrome in the rural newcomer organized population of the North is higher in patients with coronary heart disease, compared with patients with arterial hypertension. People with ischemic heart disease are more likely (40.8%) to have heart disease than those with arterial hypertension (39%). Insomnia disorders in obese patients, they are one of the contributing factors increased food intake in response to a change in emotional state against the background of "hidden" anxiety and depressive disorders. It is possible that these eating disorders and psychological status may have a negative impact on weight dynamics in the treatment of obesity, and therefore further research is needed to assess weight dynamics bodies in patients with sleep disorders. A recent meta-analysis by F. Tang et al., combining data from 18 cross-sectional and 2 prospective cohort studies showed the presence of a positive association of MS and anxiety disorders. The authors conclude that patients with MS should be targeted for and, if detected , control anxiety disorder, which can significantly improve the overall control of all components of MS meta-analysis A. Pan et al. convincingly showed bidirectional associations between MS and depressive disorders: on the one hand, the presence of depression predisposes to the formation of MS in somatically healthy individuals, and on the other – patients with MS they are more likely to suffer from depression. Several pathophysiological hypotheses have been proposed to explain the phenomenon of the association of anxiety and depressive disorders with MS. Some of them suggest the primary formation of anxiety and depression and the subsequent development of MS, others associate such an association with the influence of the formed components of MS (primarily obesity) on the psychological state of the individual. In defense of the first mentioned group of hypotheses, the following facts can testify. Firstly, as already mentioned, anxiety and depressive disorders are associated with decreased motor activity and overeating, which leads to obesity. Secondly, stress and chronic anxiety are associated with impaired functioning of the autonomic nervous system, which is manifested by an increase in heart rate and a decrease in heart rate variability. They are strictly associated with higher concentrations of glucose and triglycerides

in blood plasma, as well as higher blood pressure figures. In addition, it has been shown that anxiety disorders can lead to activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis with a high level of cortisol secretion, which has a large number of pathophysiological consequences from hypertension to obesity. It is known that the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis, in turn, is closely involved in the deposition of visceral fat and the formation of insulin resistance. It should also be borne in mind that anxiety and depressive disorders seriously affect the patient's adaptive capabilities and quality of life. Thirdly, some studies show that anxiety-depressive disorders are associated with higher levels of general inflammatory markers such as C-reactive protein, the total number of leukocytes in peripheral blood and interleukin-6.

Conclusion: According to the results of the study, it is necessary to optimize the approaches to it in the diagnosis of depressive and panic disorders in medical institutions: when talking with a patient, it is important to identify clinical signs of depression and panic disorders. Including conducting self-assessment surveys, if the clinical manifestations of psychoemotional disorders do not match the results of the questionnaire, a psychiatrist's consultation is appointed and explains to the patient the need to identify depressive and panic conditions and timely treatment.

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Информация об авторах:

Толиб М. Тураев — аспирант Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета. Самаркандия, Узбекистан; E-mail: tolibturaev544@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-2861-6579>

Чарос А. Кучимова — кандидат медицинских наук, ассистент Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета. Самаркандия, Узбекистан; E-mail: charos_kuchimova@mail.ru, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8352-3744>

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Information about the authors:

Tolib M. Turaev — basic doctoral student of Samarkand state medical university. Samarkand, Uzbekistan; E-mail: tolibturaev544@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-2861-6579>

Charos A. Kuchimova — PhD, assistant of Samarkand state medical university. Samarkand, Uzbekistan; E-mail: charos_kuchimova@mail.ru, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8352-3744>

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Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

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